

**Nano
Medicine
AUSTRIA**

Strategy Paper

version 2.0, January 2024

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Strategy Paper of the NanoMedicine-Austria Technology Platform

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This document serves as a basis for discussions with potentially supporting organizations (e.g., ministries, federal states, professional associations, foundations, etc.) as well as with organizations that may be actively involved in NanoMedicine-Austria (NM-AT) due to their thematic focus (e.g., universities, research institutions, industry, etc.).

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Executive Summary

This document describes the strategic plans and position of the Austrian Technology Platform for Nanomedicine, NM-AT, and outlines its vision and mission, core topics, goals and activities. It serves as a strategic basis for the further development of the platform and explains how NM-AT is structured and how interested organizations and individuals can get involved and interact.

Nanomedicine is the branch of medicine that uses the knowledge and tools of nanotechnology for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases. The use of nanoscale materials enables a better understanding of biological processes in the human body by focusing on the molecular and nanometric level and providing insights into tissue and cellular mechanisms that could not be studied by conventional means. Nanomedicine thus raises high expectations for better, more efficient and affordable healthcare for millions of patients and promises new solutions to improve medical treatment.

Still, nanomedicine faces various challenges, such as nano-specific characterization, the controlled manufacturing of nanoproducts especially during upscaling, or regulatory challenges due to the lack of nano-specific standards. To overcome these challenges and fully exploit the great potential of nanomedical applications, multidisciplinary collaboration between different stakeholders is required.

NM-AT brings together bio- and nanomedicine experts with the aim of increasing the visibility of nanomedicine as a benchmark for research and innovation, and promoting excellent basic and applied research to strengthen the transfer of nanomedical applications from the lab to clinical practice. It is an open platform that any interested organization or expert can join at any time, provided that the necessary expertise and interest in the platform is available.

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1. About Nanomedicine and the NanoMedicine-Austria Technology Platform

Although life expectancy has increased significantly over the last decades, the disease-free lifespan has not grown at the same rate due to lifestyle factors significantly contributing to disease burden and, therefore, reduced disease-free lifespan. However, over the long haul what can be a real game changer and therefore might revolutionize the healthcare sector for European citizens is the development of tools to understand the different biological mechanisms underlying the different types of diseases and the design of disruptive new technologies for early diagnosis, prevention and improved treatment of diseases.

Complex illnesses like cancer, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases like multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease as well as different kinds of serious inflammatory or infectious diseases (e.g., HIV) have a tremendous negative impact, not only on the patient himself but also on the whole society and are linked to social and insurance systems burden. These diseases have been key topics in the broad field of biomedical research in the past decades on a global level, and large amounts of investigations and studies have been carried out. However, appropriate diagnosis, treatments as well as preventive methods still pose one of the biggest challenges that society faces.

As one of the most promising Key Enabling Technologies (KETs), nanotechnology has provided an opportunity for the biomedical field and the healthcare sector. Nanotechnology facilitates major breakthroughs in different application sectors and thus has become the new frontier of materials and technology research, which plays an ever-increasing role in our society. Both the healthcare and the biomedical sector are just two of the sectors that have benefited from it. Moreover, nanotechnology has become a field of its own due to the miniaturization of many technologies from microchips to materials engineering or bioengineering. Crossing this border not only makes devices smaller, but also brings new phenomenology to the physics and chemistry of the devices, such as the interaction with visible light and the emergence of quantum effects on mechanical structure.

Nanomedicine is the branch of medicine that applies the knowledge and tools of nanotechnology to the prevention, diagnostics and treatment of disease. Involving the use of nanoscale materials allows a better understanding of biological processes in the human body since it focuses at the molecular and nanometric level, providing insights of tissue and cellular mechanisms that have not been able to be studied with traditional tools. Thus, nanomedicine raises high expectations for millions of patients for better, more efficient and affordable healthcare, and promises new solutions to improve medical treatments.

Over the last decade the nanomedicine field has seen its deployment as a fully-fledged sector within an organized and growing community, with national and European policies for funding research and translation that has permitted to mature an excellent research community working at a cutting-edge technology. Europe has launched different programs in Research &

Innovation (R&I) that have been crucial to address Europe's economic and societal challenges. The set of programs provide attractive and flexible funding to enable talented and creative researchers and companies to pursue the most promising avenues to develop new and innovative treatments and/or diagnostics systems and translating them from the bench to the market. Over the last years these funding programs have funded many applications ranging from nanotechnology-based biosensors to drug delivery technologies to cell biology to supramolecular chemistry with biotech applications. Moreover, several areas of medical care are already benefiting from the advantages that nanotechnology can offer.

At the same time, the use of nanotechnology and nanomaterials has raised safety concerns that need to be addressed before nanomedicine can reach patients and the market. Europe is already addressing this issue at a global level by promoting projects and initiatives that focus on the study of safety aspects, including toxicology, ecotoxicology, exposure assessment, mode of action, risk assessment and standardization, which help to ensure the environmental health and safety (EHS) of nanomaterials.

Next to that, the translation of these type of technologies from the bench to the clinics and the market is also strongly supported by the European Commission (EC) through the creation of European research infrastructures that supports the field of nanomedicine and through Public Private Partnerships creating different types of pilot plants and the Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB) for enabling nano-pharmaceutical innovative products that helps in designing and comprehension of the requirements needed for the scalability of nanodevices/nanotools and nanomedicines under Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) conditions and the regulatory pathway they need to follow.

Nanomedicine belongs to those sectors in which business development methods are not well established yet. Open issues include which type of business model fits best to start-ups and which strategies would lead them to sustained growth. With the increasing demand of innovative and better treatments and medical technologies and their applications, companies have the opportunity to expand their services in the market through different strategic approaches. These vary from product launches, acquisitions, business expansion, approvals as well as collaborations and partnerships. This is surely a good predictor of the bright future landscape of expansion of this promising area of research that Europe already supports in order for its industry to become definitive worldwide leaders in the field.

In this framework where nanomedicine currently finds itself, the Austrian technology platform “NanoMedicine-Austria” (NM-AT) aims to contribute to fostering and achieving the scientific and technological challenges in the nanomedicine field by integrating different scientific disciplines from various stakeholders.

Therefore, NM-AT builds a **common space for experts** working in (i) academia, (ii) companies from different industrial sectors such as pharma, medical technology, biotechnology and even information technologies (IT), and (iii) administration, aiming to identify and prioritize

technological, research and innovation needs in the medium and long term that shall support and empower the development in Austria of new nanomedicine-related products to reach the patient and market.

NM-AT pursues collaboration between national and international experts in the field, as well as the identification of synergies between researchers and the industrial sector, with the aim of promoting excellence in research and the transfer of results along the entire value chain, thus supporting the progress and translation of nanomedical technologies into the clinic.

2. Vision and Mission

Nanomedicine opens up fascinating new opportunities for medical applications by offering improved methods for, e.g., drug delivery systems, therapy, imaging techniques, medical devices, and diagnostic tools. The national technology platform NM-AT brings together bio- and nanomedical experts to promote science, research and translation to the clinics and the market in this field.

The NM-AT community has defined its own vision and mission, that guides the platform towards its objectives and activities.

NM-AT's vision is to increase the visibility of nanomedicine as a benchmark for research and innovation at national and international level, and promote Austria's excellent basic and applied research to strengthen the transfer of nanomedical applications from lab to clinical practice.

NM-AT's mission is to build references on Austria's nanomedical research and innovation capability, and to achieve joint impact through community-driven activities.

3. Key Topics addressed within NM-AT

Based on the five nanomedical application pillars as defined by the ETP Nanomedicine², NM-AT addresses the following **key topics**:

- **Nanotechnology-based Diagnostics**

Latest trends in nanotechnology-based diagnostics are driven by the quest for more sensitive, specific, and versatile diagnostic platforms capable of detecting diseases at early stages, monitoring response to treatment and guiding personalized therapeutic interventions. Research topics in this area include the development of new biosensors based on micro/nanotechnologies for specific diseases, the validation and analysis of new biomarkers based on nano-enabled devices, and new approaches to overcome biological barriers using nanoformulations, nanoemulsions or nanodevices.

- **Medical Imaging**

Recent advancements in medical imaging technology include the integration of micro- and nanodevices for signal detection and monitoring. These devices, which can be both non-invasive and invasive, offer unparalleled opportunities for real-time imaging and monitoring of physiological processes at cellular and molecular levels. Miniaturized imaging probes and sensors enable high-resolution imaging of biological tissues and cellular structures, providing valuable insights into disease pathology or treatment response. By leveraging the unique properties of nanomaterials, the contrast and signal-to-noise ratio of imaging modalities can be enhanced, enabling more accurate diagnosis and treatment planning.

- **Targeted drug delivery nanosystems and drug-free nanotherapeutics**

By harnessing the unique properties of nanomaterials, limitations associated with traditional drug delivery methods can be overcome and enhanced therapeutic outcomes for patients achieved. One key research area is the development of nanostructures for encapsulating new therapeutic agents. Nanoparticles, liposomes, dendrimers, and other nanocarriers serve as vehicles for delivering drugs to specific target sites within the body. These nanostructures can protect therapeutic agents from degradation, enhance their solubility and bioavailability, and facilitate their targeted delivery to diseased tissues or cells. Additionally, nanosystems can act to improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles of therapeutics.

- **Regenerative medicine**

One key area in regenerative medicine is the development of "smart" nanostructured and functionalized surfaces to enhance the biocompatibility of implants and scaffolds through surface modification techniques. By functionalizing 2D-3D materials with bioactive molecules, growth factors, or cell adhesion peptides, biomimetic interfaces

² <https://etp-nanomedicine.eu/about-nanomedicine/what-is-nanomedicine/>

that promote tissue integration and regeneration can be created. These smart surfaces play a critical role in facilitating the success of advanced therapeutic treatments, such as tissue engineering and regenerative implants.

- **Vaccines**

Research in this field includes the development of new drug delivery systems for vaccines encapsulation and nano-immunology, as well as nucleic acid nanodelivery systems that offer innovative solutions for delivering nucleic acid vaccines to target cells and tissues, protecting them from degradation and enhancing their uptake and expression.

Furthermore, NM-AT identified **additional relevant horizontal key topics** that influence and interact with all other topics:

- **Bioinformatics in nanomedicine**

Nanomedicine and bioinformatics are two cutting-edge fields at the forefront of modern healthcare and biomedical research, converging to revolutionize our understanding of diseases and the development of personalized therapeutic approaches. Nanomedicine leverages the unique properties of nanoscale materials and devices to diagnose, treat, and prevent various medical conditions with unprecedented precision and efficiency. Meanwhile, bioinformatics harnesses advanced computational techniques to analyze vast biological datasets, unraveling the complexities of genomics, proteomics, and other 'omics' data to uncover insights into disease mechanisms and inform drug discovery. Bioinformatics enable the rapid identification of potential drug targets, biomarkers, and disease pathways, accelerating drug development and facilitating the shift towards more personalized and precise healthcare solutions. By integrating nanoscale drug delivery systems and imaging agents with sophisticated computational tools, researchers can tailor therapies to individual patients, minimizing side effects and maximizing treatment efficacy. Thus, the combination of nanomedicine with bioinformatics holds immense promise for the future of medicine.

- **Nano-specific characterization**

The term nanomaterial is typically defined as materials in which one or more external dimensions of 50% or more of the particles fall within the size range of 1nm to 100nm. In the field of nanomedicine, size ranges can even extend up to 1000nm, especially in nano drug delivery. However, size remains the most critical feature, determining the nature of a nanomaterial. The size aspect is even more challenging for compound materials and processed materials which are agglomerated or formulated (e.g., by drying, spray-drying, granulation, pelletization, etc.). Developing nano-size determination methods need to be reproducible and robust even for multiple environments. Alongside with size, the surface is a determining feature of a nanomaterial due to the large surface to volume ratio in the nanoscale. Therefore,

nano-specific characterization not only needs to focus on the physicochemical properties of a product but specifically on the surface properties which often determine the nature of nanostructured systems. A further challenge of nano-specific characterization is the size of particles and often necessitates the scale down of characterization methods as well as novel developments.

- **Targeted and controlled manufacturing of nanoproducts**

Effective and safe nanostructured systems for diagnostic, therapeutic and medical applications require precise physicochemical properties (e.g., size, shape, surface properties, etc.), which depend not only on material attributes but also on the manufacturing strategies, conditions, and parameters. Hence, manufacturing must be robust, scalable, reproducible, monitorable and controllable. In particular, we need to find a way to bridge the translation from small- and lab-scale academic development to large-scale commercial production. This requires close collaboration between research, industry and regulatory agencies. In addition, the implementation of quality by design concepts, process analytical technologies, and control concepts must be promoted, and the use of predictive modeling, machine learning, and artificial intelligence must be pursued.

- **Standardization**

One of the challenges for the translation of nanomedicine approaches into clinical practice and for regulatory approval of these products is the limited availability of suitable standards to ensure quality, safety, consistency, repeatability, and accuracy. In this respect, measurement standards are crucial, e.g., for the size determination of nano-products. No less important, however, are standards of characteristics, standards of practice (procedures and guidelines), application standards and standards for verification (e.g., reference materials). The required standardization efforts need considerable contributions from the academic community, the relevant industry as well as national and international standardization bodies and close collaboration between them.

Figure 1 illustrates the NM-AT key topics described above.

In 2024, the extent to which these topics are representative and relevant for the Austrian nanomedicine community will be evaluated, and their subtopics will be refined and specified.

Based on a survey, current R&D&I trends within the Austrian nanomedicine expert ecosystem will be mapped and evaluated in order to better understand the Austrian nanomedicine landscape.

Figure 1. Key topics addressed within the NM-AT platform.

4. Goals and Activities

Specific objectives have been defined within NM-AT, which are pursued jointly with the members of the platform. The NM-AT goals are:

- Tackle medical challenges to achieve a more efficient and affordable healthcare, as well as development of new solutions to improve medical treatments
- Connect different multidisciplinary experts in the nanomedical field (e.g., biologists, physicists, biochemists, clinicians, pharmacists, etc.) belonging to all type of actors (i.e., academia, research centers, SMEs, industry, hospitals, healthcare system)
- Create synergies through multidisciplinary cooperation among the different actors
- Support the Austrian nanomedical community and link it to European and global nanomedicine related initiatives
- Enhance access to national and international research projects and funding
- Facilitate close collaboration with industry to allow large-scale manufacturing and production of efficient and safe nanopharmaceuticals
- Provide support in nanosafety, quality and sustainability aspects to meet regulatory requirements

To achieve the set goals, NM-AT will perform several activities:

- Organize regular meetings and networking activities
 - Regular Chairs Meetings
 - Biannual Board Meetings
 - Annual webinar and/or networking event
- Refine and update the platform's strategy
- Contribute to relevant position papers
- Generate and collect possible topics and ideas, and contribute them to national and/or international funding agencies
- Support in the organization of workshops and trainings for students and early-stage researchers in different nanomedicine-related topics
- Support with grant applications
- Create outreach to relevant stakeholders, including targeted public communication

The platform activities as well as news and announcements are made available via the **NM-AT website** (<https://www.nanomedicine-austria.at/>) and the **NM-AT LinkedIn account** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/nanomedicine-austria>).

NM-AT Objectives

Table 1 summarizes the short-term, mid-term and long-term objectives of the platform which are planned to be achieved until end of 2026.

Table 1. Short-term, mid-term and long-term objectives of NM-AT and their KPIs.

Short-term objectives to be achieved until Dec. 2024	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Increase the platform's visibility	No. of followers at LinkedIn: >200; No. of new postings on LinkedIn: >10
Better understand the Austrian nanomedical R&D&I infrastructure and identify further key player	Mini-survey with Austrian nanomedical key players shared & evaluated
Mid-term objectives to be achieved until Dec. 2025	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Attract new organizations and expand the NM-AT community	No. of organizations in Board of Members: >25
Better understand the international nanomedical R&D&I infrastructure and identify further key player	List with international nanomedical key players available
Long-term objectives to be achieved until Dec. 2026	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Contribute to relevant position papers	Involvement of at least one NM-AT member in the position paper contribution process
Communicate with funding agencies & increase visibility of nanomedicine-related content in funding programs (national/international)	One or more nanomedical call topic(s) included into funding schemes

NM-AT Work Plan

Evaluation of activities in 2023 and planning 2024

Table 2 provides an overview of the key activities carried out in 2023, while Table 3 gives an outlook on the planned activities in 2024 and how their achievement will be assessed.

Table 2. Performed key activities in 2023, and their KPIs.

Performed Key Activities in 2023	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Keep the platform and its members active: Regular Chairs and two Board Meetings organized	Meeting minutes of Chairs Meetings available, presentation slides of two Board Meetings shared with all Board members
Increase the platform visibility and support early career researchers: Sponsoring of the Best Talk Award at BioNanoMed 2023 conference	News entry on NM-AT website and LinkedIn available; Increase in No. of followers in LinkedIn to 173 (+77)
Link NM-AT to the international nanomedicine community: Contribution to CLINAM 2023	4 oral presentations and 1 poster presentation contributed by NM-AT members
Update of the platform's strategy: NM-AT Strategy Paper version 2.0 created	Draft internally available and ready to be published early 2024

Table 3. Planned key activities in 2024, and their KPIs.

Planned Key Activities in 2024	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Organize regular Chair Meetings and two Board Meetings (Q2 & Q4 2024)	Meeting minutes and presentation sides available
Conduct a mini-survey to map and evaluate current R&D&I trends within the Austrian nanomedicine expert ecosystem	Survey responses received and evaluated, results published on NM-AT website and LinkedIn
Release and promotion of the NM-AT strategy paper version 3.0	Updated Strategy Paper publicly accessible via the NM-AT website in Q4 2024
Participate in min. 2 scientific conferences related to nanomedicine (e.g., 14th World Meeting on Pharmaceutics, Biopharmaceutics and Pharmaceutical Technology; 19 th Annual ETPN Event)	>2 oral or poster presentations contributed by NM-AT members
Raise awareness and promote Austrian research in the field of nanomedicine	Latest scientific publications from the NM-AT community shared on the NM-AT website and on LinkedIn
Support in grant applications	Decision of a COST Action proposal on nanomedicine taken by the Board (y/n)

5. Organizational Structure and Coordination

The platform was launched in 2016 and has been active both nationally and internationally over the past years. The overall platform organizational structure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Structure and organization of the NM-AT platform.

General Coordinator: NM-AT is coordinated and organized by BNN (BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH³). The General Coordinator from the BNN team, Susanne Resch, takes care of the administrative and organizational activities of the platform (e.g., scheduling and organizing meetings and other platform events, facilitating exchange between the members, monitoring and reporting about activities, etc.), and builds the central communication point for all matters. Next to that, the BNN team is responsible for the external appearance and communication, and operates the NM-AT website⁴ and social media channel⁵.

Chairs: The platform is scientifically guided by currently four nominated Chairs⁶ with complementary expertise. The Chairs are in close exchange with the General Coordinator and committed to their role for the period from June 2022 until June 2024.

³ <https://www.bnn.at/>

⁴ <http://www.nanomedicine-austria.at/>

⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nanomedicine-austria/>

⁶ <https://www.nanomedicine-austria.at/organization/>

Figure 3. The nominated Chairs and their NM-AT key horizontal topic.

Core Group: The Core Group is composed of the Chairs and the General Coordinator. Together, they develop and implement the strategic direction of the platform. The members of the Core Group are also involved in strategic development activities at European level (e.g., preparation of roadmaps, positioning of specific topics, etc.), and are responsible to establish links between NM-AT and other relevant (inter-)national initiatives.

Board of Members: Austrian organizations that actively participate in the activities of the platform form the Board of Members. They contribute to events and provide input and feedback to the strategic development of the platform.

Figure 4. Austrian organizations that build the Board of Members (as of Dec., 2023).

Wider community: Other interested organizations that are not part of the Board of Members (Non-Austrian experts or organizations) can still interact and collaborate with NM-AT, e.g., regarding co-organizing events, sharing information, building international Consortia for future projects, etc.

Table 4. Overview of the roles within the NM-AT organization and their responsibilities.

Role	Main responsibilities
General Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Organize all NM-AT meetings and events• Serve as central communication point for all matters• Update the NM-AT website and LinkedIn account• Monitor all NM-AT activities & report to the Board
Chairs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Scientifically guide the platform & all NM-AT activities• Attend regular Chair meetings & biannual Board meetings
Core Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Develop NM-AT Strategy Paper• Develop annual working plans & set priorities for defined periods
Board of Members	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Support the implementation of all NM-AT activities• Provide feedback on NM-AT Strategy Paper• Attend biannual Board meetings and networking event

6. Potential Engagement of Stakeholder Groups

Connecting different stakeholders in the nanomedical area form the basis for networking and interactions, both in terms of goal setting and achievement. The following list represents an overview of NM-AT's stakeholders:

- Scientific community (Universities, research organizations, academic institutes, etc.)
- Industry (large companies, SMEs, start-ups, etc.) and their representative institutions
- Regional, national and international public bodies (e.g., ministries, national and international funding agencies, etc.) and standardization organizations
- European, international and national platforms related and/or complementary to NM-AT
- General public

Each stakeholder group can engage with NM-AT in different ways. The levels of engagement are divided into the following:

1. Active participation by NM-AT members (e.g., participation in meetings, scientific presentations at events, contribution to project proposals and/or scientific publications, etc.)
2. Financial support (e.g., funding projects, sponsoring events, etc.)
3. Wider outreach (e.g., creating awareness, increasing visibility, establishing links to other initiatives, etc.)

Who can become a member of NM-AT?

NM-AT is an open platform to which any interested organization or expert can potentially contribute and participate at any time, as long as the necessary expertise and interest in the nanomedical field is provided. In addition, potential new members should support and appreciate the platform's objectives and operating principles.

The platform thrives on the activity and competence of different key players who actively contribute to the further development of the platform. The key players of NM-AT cover different disciplines and areas of expertise, which are crucial for the development, application and commercial implementation of nanomedical solutions. New interested parties are welcome to join the Austrian nanomedical community!

How to become a member of NM-AT?

Written interest in membership can be expressed via the contact form of the NM-AT platform: <https://www.nanomedicine-austria.at/contact/>

7. International Cooperation

NM-AT is an Austrian-based platform that is open to international cooperation on various related and/or complementary activities. It particularly values all nanomedicine-focused initiatives on a global level. Therefore, NM-AT is actively looking for international cooperation activities to connect the Austrian community with other existing global platforms and networks. Listed below are some key initiatives with which NM-AT has already established (or plans to establish in the future) collaborations:

- European Technology Platforms:
 - ETP NanoMedicine⁷
- European Partnerships and Initiatives:
 - Innovative Health Initiative⁸
 - International Consortium for Personalized Medicine⁹
 - European Federation for Pharmaceutical Sciences¹⁰
 - European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases¹¹

⁷ <https://etp-nanomedicine.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.ihp.europa.eu/>

⁹ <https://www.icpermed.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.eufeps.org/start.html>

¹¹ <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

- Other Austrian Technology Platforms:
 - Austrian Platform for Personalized Medicine¹²
 - Advanced Microfluidics Initiative¹³
 - PROMETHEUS Network on Regenerative Medicine¹⁴
- COST Actions:
 - CA17104 STRATAGEM¹⁵ and PANDORA¹⁶
- Open Innovation Test Beds
 - PHOENIX¹⁷ Open Innovation Test Bed for enabling nano-pharmaceutical innovative products
 - NextGenMicrofluidics¹⁸ Next generation test bed for upscaling of microfluidic devices based on nano-enabled surfaces and membranes

Further initiatives are welcomed to get in touch with NM-AT to explore collaboration potentials and identify synergies.

¹² <https://www.personalized-medicine.at/>

¹³ <http://www.microfluidics-initiative.com/>

¹⁴ <http://www.prometheus-netzwerk.at/>

¹⁵ <https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA17104/>

¹⁶ <https://www.cost.eu/actions/IG17104/>

¹⁷ <https://www.phoenix-oitb.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.nextgenmicrofluidics.eu/>

Nanomedicine.

Small Scale.

Big Impact.